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How can a newly established journal attract foreign authors?

The geographical diversity of the origin of both editorial staff and authors is one of the crucial criteria in the selection of journals for international recognized databases (Scopus, Web of Science, etc.). The established world-class scientific journals, as a rule, have their own readership, regular authors, and attract new ones due to their own high indicators (Hirsch index, quartile, etc.).

Many newly established periodicals aiming at international recognition face the issues of finding foreign editors and authors. It is more difficult for the journals that are not included in recognized databases to compete with more recognized ones in attracting new authors.

As a result of evaluations of journals, the members of the Scopus Content Selection & Advisory Board (CSAB) indicate that journals need to significantly expand their international reach in terms of authorship and academic influence. They recommend them to consider publishing more articles in English and to attract more respected authors from other countries. The recommendation is undoubtedly valuable, but the question arises: how to attract foreign authors?

In fact, the targeted e-mail distribution as a tool for finding authors and increasing publication activity is poorly effective, since authors are mainly interested in recognized journals indexed in international scientometric databases.

Another recommendation from the expert is that it will be helpful if the published articles cover a wider range of research topics and issues that may directly affect an international audience.

As N.V. Kirillova rightly notes: “no scientific work can be started without preliminary study and analysis of research carried out earlier on the chosen topic or taking place at present. The results of such an analysis of publications on the topic of research are reflected directly in scientific articles and published in the form of independent systematic reviews.”*

In conjunction with the foregoing, it is important to reconsider the duties of the members of the editorial board as the direct authors of the newly established journal, who could, for example, on the instructions of the editor-in-chief write up-to-date reviews on the relevant problems and headings of the journal. Published articles can be sent directly to foreign authors, which are cited by the authors who are members of the editorial board. Alternatively, this can induce foreign authors to a scientific dialogue, and, possibly, to publish articles in a newly established journal.

* Kirillova, O.V. (ed.). (2017). Methodological recommendations for the drawing up and design of scientific articles in journals indexed in international scientometric databases. Association of Scientific Editors and Publishers. Moscow, 2017.

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